

Daphni (Μονή Δαφνίου)

By Justin Mann, Dumbarton Oaks

Entry tags: Greece, Attica, Religious Group, Monasticism, Religious Place, Orthodoxy

The monastery of Daphni is located to the west of Athens, Greece, and maintains a prominent position along the Iera Odos (Sacred Way). The monastery is dedicated to the Dormition of the Virgin and represents one of the architectural jewels of Middle Byzantine Greek architecture. The katholikon of the monastery is in the domed-octagon style that typifies the so-called "Helladic" school of architecture, such as is seen at its architectural predecessor, Hosios Loukas. The interior of the structure is decorated by an impressive cycle of gold mosaics that is highlighted by an imposing depiction of Christ Pantokrator in the central dome. Yet, even in light of clearly great effort and expenditure that went into the monastery's construction and decoration, little is known of its origins or founder. The monastery is noted only in two brief abstracts that reveal relatively little about Daphni's history. Based on art and architectural comparison, however, it seems the monastery was constructed sometime around 1080 CE and remained in function until the arrival of the Crusaders in the early thirteenth century, when it was taken over by Cistercian monks. In later years, the monastery took under various functions. It was used as a military headquarters during the Greek Revolution, as a barracks by Bavarian troops in the 1830s, and public mental hospital in the 1880s. The monastery is currently an archaeological site under the jurisdiction of the Greek Ministry of Culture and Sports (Western Attica Ephoreia) and is listed as a UNESCO World Heritage Site.

Date Range: 1080 CE - 1458 CE

Region: Western Attica

Region tags: Greece, Attica

Location of the monastery of Daphni.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Bouras, Ch. 1998. "The Daphni Monastic Complex Reconsidered." In *Αετός*, Studies in Honour of C. Mango, edited by I. Ševčenko and I. Hutter, 1-15. Stuttgart: B.G. Teubner.
- Source 2: Cormack, R. 2008. "Rediscovering the Christ Pantokrator at Daphni." *Journal of the Warburg and Courtauld Institutes* 71: 55-74.
- Source 3: Diez, E. and O. Demus. 1931. *Byzantine Mosaics in Greece, Hosios Lucas and Daphni*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/537>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Subject of current excavations and renovations by the Greek Ministry of Culture.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: Current

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Research by the Greek Ministry of Culture (Western Attica Ephoreia).

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: Mount Aigaleo

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Trackway or road-surface

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ A group of structures:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: The monastery is made up several major structures, that span the monastery's life. First, the katholikon (abbey church) makes up the core of the monastery. The second major building is the refectory, which was built just to the katholikon's northwest. To the south, is a group of buildings containing a bath complex. At some point, a small free-standing chapel was also built but it is no longer present.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

↳ In modernity

DRAFT

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The dome of the monastery collapsed at some point in the 18th century and was rebuilt. The Greek Ministry of Culture also saw to the renovations of the narthex. The monastery was again recently restored in the 2010s and has been reopened to visitors. Archaeological and restoration works continue on the site.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

DRAFT

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is little to no documentation surviving that addresses Daphni's early foundation. However, given the size and grandeur of the architecture and mosaics, it is very likely that an elite segment of Byzantine society sponsored the monastery's construction.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: In the current state of knowledge about Daphni, it's impossible to say with certainty

why the monastery was founded. However, it is likely spiritual motivation was accompanied by economic and political goals.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: There are the remains of a possible scriptorium at the site.

↳ What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:

DRAFT

– Type: Unknown, but given the status as an Orthodox Christian monastery, likely Christian texts or monastic documents.

↳ Were the scriptures/sacred texts located in a specific room within the main structure:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ In the cella:

The cella refers to the most interior area of the structure, often where the cult statue(s) might be located.

DRAFT

– No

↳ In a restricted section of the structure removed from general traffic:

This would be a back-room or remote part of the structure, i.e. Opisthodomoi in Greek temples, etc

DRAFT

– No

↳ Space underneath the structure

DRAFT

– No

↳ Other:

DRAFT

– Other [specify]: Possibly located in the scriptorium, to the katholikon's south.

↳ Where are the scriptures/sacred texts located in secondary building:

DRAFT

– Yes

↳ Built specifically for the purpose:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: Possibly located in the so-called "scriptorium" identified to the katholikon's south.

↳ Repurposed:

DRAFT

– No

↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:

DRAFT

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unclear, but very likely.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 50

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 16.5

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood
– Field doesn't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– No

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: There is a crypt, presumably for monks and local patrons. However, there are also the tombs of crusader lords, particularly the de la Roche family that ruled over the Duchy of Athens.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Used as the burial place for the Latin dukes of the Duchy of Athens.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– No

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: The monks in the monastic community

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:
– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:
– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Do rituals occur at this place:
Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.
– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

DRAFT

– Yes

Notes: The main group would have been Orthodox monks whose practices would have been governed by the monastery's typikon (foundation charter).

↳ Present full time
– Yes

↳ Present part time
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although there is no evidence at present, it is very likely there was a formal bureaucracy.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no textual evidence to prove that Daphni controlled economic resources, but this must have been the case as demonstrated by other Byzantine monasteries.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: With more evidence, the answer would likely emerge that Daphni did, in some respects, provide services for the local community.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Daphni likely would have stored tax documents and land grants at the monastery, among other secular documents.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Field doesn't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Daphni (Μονή Δαφνίου), Cormack, Robin. "Rediscovering the Christ Pantocrator at Daphni" 71, no. 1 (January 1, 2008). <https://doi.org/10.1086/jwci20462776>.

Reference: Daphni (Μονή Δαφνίου), Millet, Gabriel. "Mosaïques De Daphni" 19, no. 1 (1895). <https://doi.org/10.3406/bch.1895.3655>.